

WAYS TO IMPROVE THE MARKETING ACTIVITY OF "JOZIBA TRANS" JSC

Musayeva Shaira Azimovna

Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8417154>

Abstract. *In this article, the improvement and development of marketing activities in the enterprise, the provision of affordable and high-quality services to the population, the creation of economic and legal access, integration in the fields of production and other services, the creation of an effective mechanism for the state regulation of the production and trade sector, after-sales service improving the quality and timely delivery of services, being active in social networks, and promoting one's trade brand.*

Keywords: *enterprise, marketing service, integration, product, brand, competition, market.*

Introduction. Due to the socio-economic reforms implemented in Uzbekistan, the implementation of national programs clearly and carefully developed by the leader of our country and our government, the favorable conditions and opportunities created by our state for entrepreneurs, and the appropriate incentives for investments, development in all economic indicators in our country. rates are being monitored.

Today, Samarkand region is one of the developed regions of our republic in the fields of industry, agriculture, trade, transport and service. A number of positive works are being carried out in our region to ensure stable growth in all sectors of the economy and to deepen reforms in the social sphere.

The company always pays serious attention to marketing. After all, being a wholesale company, it always deals with customers. This implies the constant development of relations with marketing. If we look at the state of organization of marketing activities in the company's activities, the company is using market- and product-oriented organizational structures of marketing according to the 4 main organizational structures of marketing service organization. And its structure is as follows.

The organizational structure of marketing activities based on product production allows enterprises to better adapt to the market requirements for each product and to produce products with different production technologies, a short life cycle, and high innovation requirements.

A market-oriented organizational structure of a marketing service in an enterprise is a type of marketing management structure in which managers of individual markets are responsible for the development and implementation of strategies and plans for marketing activities in specific markets. The market-oriented organizational structure of the marketing service is illustrated in the diagram below in studying the activity of the enterprise, the working status of marketing concepts and its availability were studied. In particular, the company's purposeful use of the concept of sales and marketing attracted my attention. That is, while the enterprise is engaged in wholesale trade today, attention is being paid to further strengthening relations with customers, to fully satisfy its capabilities, and to intensify the relationship of marketing experts to their work. In addition, digital marketing concepts are also being used to receive orders. Advertisements and discounts are being announced through social networks.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. Today, as a result of increasing attention to marketing activities, the company has developed a marketing plan, which is formulated as follows.

Table 1

Marketing plan of "Joziba trans" JSC

<i>Departments</i>	<i>Content</i>
Enter	Brief summaries in plan sections
1. Market situation and its prospects	Analysis of information about the marketing environment, consumers, competitors and their goods, sales channels.
2. Analysis of enterprise opportunities	Contributing factors and risk assessment.
3. Financial and marketing goals and objectives	Net profit, sales volume, market share, price level, advertising coverage and other indicators.
4. Implementation of marketing strategy	Problems, ways to solve them and options.
5. Action program	What to do? When? Who is responsible for this? What should be the result? How much does it cost? answers to the questions are found.
6. Budgets	Comparison of results and costs
7. Control and ordering	Analysis of effectiveness and conducting activities to change the actions in the plan.

In the study of enterprise activity, I focused mainly on working with data on the wholesale trade of food products.

Apart from trade, one of the main activities of the enterprise is the provision of household services and services. Today, the enterprise provides the following services to the population:

- telephone, electronic goods repair services;
- PayNet services;
- Transport services and others.

Table 2

Status of providing household paid services to the population of "Joziba Trans" JSC in 2020-2022

No	Service types	Unit of measure	2021 year	2022 year	2023* year
1.	Transport services	thousand soums	63491.3	66237.2	67436.1
2.	Telephone, electronic goods repair services	thousand soums	623.4	649.1	964.2
3.	PayNet services	thousand soums	6482.4	6528.4	6829.1
	Total	thousand soums	78509.3	81254.4	123869.3

As can be seen from the table, the enterprise also provides services to the population. In particular, by the end of 2022, transport services worth 66,237.2 thousand soums, telephone and

electronic goods repair services worth 649.1 thousand soums, PayNet services worth 6528.4 thousand soums have been provided.

Price policy of the enterprise: when concluding a sales contract, suppliers and buyers must determine the price at which the product will be sold. The price of the goods is determined by the department of planning and economy based on the cost of production. Calculation is done for each product. There is a strict rule when determining the price: the price should not be lower than the cost. In addition to costs, the price includes statutory taxes. When calculating the selling price of a product unit, the following costs are allocated and the following approaches are used:

Table 3

Costs in calculating the selling price of a product unit

No	Name of cost items	Calculation method
<i>Direct costs</i>		
1.	Raw material	Discounted prices
1.1	Raw material	Raw materials are the basic and additional resources necessary for the production of products. Baked clay, soil and cheperitsa are the main raw materials for construction products.
1.2	Supporting materials	As per direct material consumption rates approved by Chief Engineer
2.	Water	In accordance with the norms of water and heat energy consumption approved by the Chief Engineer.
3.	Salaries of key production employees:	It includes the wages of production workers and other workers directly related to the production of products, performance of work and provision of services, as well as payments for time not worked (absent) stipulated by the labor legislation.
<i>Additional costs</i>		
4.	Additional costs	Accounting is carried out in the conditions of production facilities that produce certain types of products and semi-finished products.
5.	Common usage costs	Accounting is maintained for the entire company. The apportionment method is applied in direct proportion to the wages of the main production workers for each type of product, work and service.
6.	Shipping costs	If necessary, according to the contract, the sale price can be calculated taking into account the costs associated with their transportation. In this case, the transport costs in the calculation are allocated as a separate item.

Cost analysis is the most important cost management tool. Its main goal is to identify opportunities for more rational use of production resources, reduce production and sales costs, and ensure profit growth. Dynamic analysis of cost indicators allows to evaluate changes in production and financial activity of the enterprise, to forecast for the future.

The grouping of costs by elements is unified and mandatory, and allows controlling the formation, structure and dynamics of costs through systems that describe their economic content.

It is necessary to study the ratio of actual and past labor, to standardize and analyze inventories, to calculate specific indicators of the turnover of working capital, and to study other calculations of the industrial and general economic level. The analysis of the elemental composition and structure of production costs allows determining the main directions of searching for reserves depending on the level of material, labor and capital intensity of production.

Table 4

Costs of sales activities at the enterprise in 2021-2022 and their dynamics

Cost elements	2021 year		2022 year	
	All, million. soum	Specificity in trading costs, %	All, million. soum	Specificity in trading costs, %
Material costs:	35000	73.22	50700	77.29
raw material	31000	64.85	45000	68.60
energy resources	4000	8.37	5700	8.69
labor costs	10000	20.9	11500	17.5
contributions for social needs	3200	6.7	3300	5.0
Depreciation	450	0.9	510	0.8
other expenses	1380	2.9	1800	2.7
Trading expenses, total	47800	100	65600	100
Products for sale	49600		68600	

To a greater extent, this indicator provides a clear correlation with profit: an increase in costs leads to a decrease in profit per ruble of production, and vice versa. Among its disadvantages, this indicator can be affected by many subjective and objective factors, that is, it does not depend on the quality of work of the enterprise team.

Selling manufactured products is also considered as an important marketing event. The range of products will also expand during the sales process. Each enterprise is required to have its own sales channels in the organization of product sales. As sales channels, intermediaries who take ownership of goods participate in the delivery of products from the producer to the consumer.

Today, most businesses are setting up sales outlets on their balance sheet to sell their products. In general, the importance of wholesale trade enterprises in the delivery of goods to the final consumer is increasing. This prevents the transfer of goods to other persons. It will have the ability to control the competition and influence the buyers.

In the main days of the internship period, I studied the results of the employees' activities and the characteristics of labor resources of "Joziba Trans" JSC. That is, the goods sold by the enterprise, labor resources of the enterprise, economic indicators were analyzed.

As can be seen from the table, the total number of employees of "Joziba Trans" JSC will be 56 people by the end of 2022, which has increased by 8 people compared to 2021. Labor productivity increased by 125.1 percent or 1.25 times. In 2022, the production volume per capita increased from 40,585,000 to 50,789,000 soums. In 2022, the average monthly salary of employees decreased from 4,966,000 soums to 4,771,000 soums, that is, it increased by 96.0%.

5 marketers and 5 sales department employees work in the company's marketing service department. Their share in the total number of employees is also good. After all, in today's rapidly developing era, the role of marketing is incomparable. For this reason, the marketing department also operates in this enterprise.

Table 5

""Joziba trans" JSC dynamics of labor resources

No	Indicators	Unit of measure	2021	2022	2023*	The ratio of 2022 to 2021	
						+;-	percent, %
1.	Average number of employees	person	48	56	65	+8	116.6
2.	Average monthly salary of employees	thousand soums	4 966.0	4 771.0	5 309.0	-195	96.0
3.	Labor productivity	thousand soums	40585	50789	65888	+10204	125.1

Since the products produced in the textile sector in our republic are considered the main consumer goods, improving the mechanism of promoting their trade will help not only to fill the domestic consumer market, but also to speed up the production process.

One of the main directions of economic reforms carried out in construction products trade is to meet the needs of a large segment of the population for various consumer goods and other services at a high level and quality.

Trading system measures the transformation of products into goods, at the same time, the sales process is the main factor that forms the quality, appearance and consumer requirements for the manufactured products. This situation allows to coordinate the production process with modern market requirements.

Sales promotion system based on short-term measures to attract customers, quick services.

PR system mainly serves the enterprise to introduce buyers to a certain type of sales assistance.

In marketing practice, the system of demand formation in the sale of products aims at long-term strategic goals, while the system of sales promotion aims at more immediate strategic goals. Therefore, the use of both systems in relation to each other ensures the efficiency of the sales process. In particular, Advertising, which is considered the main element of the demand formation system, plays an important role in increasing the volume of sales.

In today's competitive conditions, light industrial enterprises in the region use little marketing tools for sales market research and attracting customers, or rather, they do not need such processes. The reason is that the main product of spinning enterprises is raw material because its buyers are clear. However, in sewing and knitting enterprises, the market is already realizing the need for a very strong set of actions not only to enter foreign markets, but also to sell products in the domestic market. Therefore, special infrastructures supporting the market activity of enterprises have been formed in our country and their activities are being developed.

Direct marketing and event marketing activities have not been formed as the enterprise activity is still a newly formed enterprise. For this reason, we have developed proposals for direct and event marketing activities in leading international and local trade enterprises. During my research, I got acquainted with the elements of direct marketing in the activities of several wholesale enterprises in Uzbekistan and made an offer for the enterprise. Today, the company is fully implementing its communication policy. The company's communication policy is the

implementation of measures to promote goods in the market: conducting advertising campaigns, providing relevant benefits and discounts to intermediaries and consumers, encouraging employees involved in product sales.

Table 6

Advertising means of the enterprise and ways of shaping public opinion

Visiting papers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Must be of high quality and professionally prepared. - Must provide detailed contact information about your company in your native language, English or another foreign language. - All employees must have business cards prepared in a uniform style.
Brochures and catalogs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It should be of high quality. - It should be short, informative and visually appealing.
Buyer and of customers testimonies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recommend your products and services with confidence they should do. - By your best and most loyal customers and clients, preferably by their top management. - These testimonials should be included in your advertising brochures.
Journal and in newspapers articles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Must clearly describe your company as a market leader. - Your brochures should be quoted. - It should be hung in your office. - Must be sent to your authorized buyers and clients.
Video material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Must be taken professionally. - Must be interesting, informative and easy to find. - It should show the best qualities of your goods and services. - It should be short, have a clear and targeted advertising idea.
Website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In terms of content, it should be deep and rich in information, its appearance should be immediately noticeable and attract attention. - Must be professionally prepared and regularly updated. - The possibility of electronic question-and-answer exchange should be available. - If necessary, it should be possible to order and buy online.

Source: Student development based on company data.

The complex of marketing communications of the enterprise is inseparable from the development strategy information system marketing tools (for example, direct marketing, advertising) that facilitate the exchange of ideas (knowledge) about the enterprise's products, its reputation with existing and potential consumers or customers and ensure its stability, public relations, etc.) is a competition. competitive environment. Marketing requires the manager to combine production and sales into a single process and possess the qualities of a competent planner. Marketing communications allows not only to identify latent needs for a specific product or service and to promote and advertise them at the appropriate place and time, but also to conduct research and practical pricing, forecasting and financing, product distribution and combines control.

Thomas Gad is a practicing advertiser and scholar of branding policy, who studies the scientific and practical aspects of branding policy about successful brands. Any theory of branding

must first propose a model, a structure of the brand, in simple terms, a set of shelves on which brands are placed.

Thus, Thomas Gad offers his collection of four shelves, which he calls Dimensions, for greater stability. By the way, that's why this book is called "4D Branding". These 4 dimensions are said to be:

1. Functional dimension (related to the usefulness of the product or service associated with the brand).

2. Social dimension (refers to the ability to identify oneself with a certain social group).

3. Moral dimension (perception of global or local responsibility). It includes the moral values shared by the brand and its consumers.

4. Mental dimension (the ability to support a person). Simply put, a brand provides a personalized consumer experience.

I also developed the enterprise trademark and analyzed the 4D model of the brand logo as follows. Growth opportunities are presented as this brand business is engaged in trading activities. In addition, the name of the enterprise and the activity it is engaged in are given in capital letters.

Brand equity gives the consumer a sense of satisfaction in using it. The following scheme is used for their development:

- the product must be reliable;
- to be comfortable;
- should be useful.

In addition, there are emotional values:

- the product should give a sense of independence;
- to be dignified;
- friendliness;
- conservatism.

Before you can create that value, you need to understand who your audience is and what their needs and wants are. Prospect research is the first and most important step in developing a brand identity. When consumers are studied, you know what they expect from the company. It remains to record the most relevant values and use them for promotion.

In today's developing social networks, we can try our hand at promoting the company's brand. The reason is that the role of social networks in all aspects is incomparable today.

The company does not use any social networks today. For this reason, I developed personal profiles of the company on Instagram, Telegram, Facebook and YouTube networks and developed suggestions for promoting and improving the brand.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS.

Today, the enterprise is considered one of the leading production companies in the district. The enterprise pays great attention to the construction of small and large buildings, and more attention is paid to the low wastage in the use of production products in the enterprise.

Historically, and even now, there is a view of production and production work as one of the leading sectors for the country. In fact, the role of production in the development of social relations and meeting the needs of the population is incomparable.

Regulation of the production sector by the state, the state exerts its influence on the economic activities of society based on the needs of the population, in order to improve the social situation, through economic and social policy, with legal, administrative, economic supports and methods. must be understood.

We believe that it is appropriate to carry out the following tasks in order to improve and develop trade activities in the enterprise:

- creation of economic and legal access to affordable and high-quality services to the population;
- creation of mechanisms for the development of the process of integration and cooperation in the fields of production and other services;
- creation of an effective mechanism of state regulation of production and trade;
- activation and acceleration of activities of production organizations protecting consumer rights;
- improvement of logistic systems in enterprise activity;
- improving the quality of after-sales service and improving timely service;
- be active in social networks and promote your brand

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